

A large, stylized graphic of a plant stem and leaves. The stem is a thick, light green line that curves from the bottom left towards the top right. Several dark green, oval-shaped leaves are attached to the stem. At the bottom left, a thick, brown, curved shape represents the soil or a hand holding the plant.

ISLANDR Roadmap

Part 2: Single site journey

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Summary

This deliverable gives a summary description of the ISLANDR Roadmap journey of single sites. The ISLANDR Roadmap is a decision-making tool designed to support users engaged in contaminated site management and land redevelopment. Recognising the complexity of the remediation process, the roadmap does not prescribe a rigid set of steps but instead offers structured guidance to navigate key decisions. While it cannot map every possible choice in advance, it provides a clear direction to help users make informed and effective decisions. Adaptable to different contexts, the roadmap can be tailored to deliver user-specific insights, ensuring relevance and practical value for diverse remediation projects. The Roadmap consists of three journeys: single sites, portfolio of sites and diffuse soil contamination, and those journeys are described in separate reports.

Keywords

Sustainable Risk-based Land Management, contaminated sites, brownfields, soil health, circularity, low input remediation, contaminants of emerging concern, wider benefits, wider value, spatial planning, ISLANDR Roadmap

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CEC	Contaminants of emerging concern
CSM	Conceptual Site Model
PRA.MS	Preliminary Risk Assessment Model for the identification and assessment of problem areas for Soil contamination in Europe European Commission
SPR	Source, pathway, receptor

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ISLANDR project in brief

The Information-based Strategies for Land Remediation, in short ISLANDR, is a multidisciplinary project, which is foremost aimed at supporting the execution of the EU mission: A Soil Deal for Europe.

More specifically, the ISLANDR research activities are designed to provide tools and methods so as to support: (1) the delineation of polluted soils across Europe, (2) an evidence-based assessment of the risks posed by polluted soils, (3) the promotion of sustainable and risk-based land management practices, (4) the inclusion of a wider valuation approach in financial and investment cases, and (5) a closer integration of land contamination and spatial planning decision-making. Lessons learnt and experience gained throughout the project duration will be used to (6) deliver key policy-relevant findings related to the Soil Strategy, the new Soil Health Law, and other areas of policy where soils are crucial.

In order to road-test the project's findings, seven test areas across Europe have been identified. To begin with, the ISLANDR Test Areas (ITAs) will provide a real-world context for the planned research activities. More concretely, the ITAs have been selected to cover different land use types, such as urban, peri-urban, rural, agro-forestry, mining, wetlands and coastal areas. Furthermore, the ITAs are characterized by both point source and diffuse pollution, as well as by different soil pollution types, such as organic, inorganic, as well as contaminants of emerging concern.

Furthermore, ISLANDR brings a dedicated focus to low input remediation, by including test areas impacted by the consequences of the green transition, such as former mining areas. This will ensure that soil remediation will be facilitated even when the cost of remediation is economically marginal or may even be negative. On the one hand, this necessitates a more thorough understanding of low input remediation approaches from a technological perspective, yet it also requires a wider value proposition for investment cases and financial planning.

Key actors, stakeholders and end-beneficiaries are at the epicentre of ISLANDR. Through roundtables in the respective ITAs, the foremost assignment of local actors will be to provide feedback and offer insights as to the robustness and effectiveness of the strategies, frameworks and decision-support tools, as well as on the wider valuation approaches and financing mechanisms to be developed over the course of the project's lifetime. Thus, the Roundtables are foreseen to bring an iterative feedback loop to the research process, with a view to ensure the wider uptake of the project's outcomes and achievements.

Last but not least, local communities in the respective ITAs will be invited to participate in a survey organized both during the early stages and towards the end of the project, as a means to document soil literacy among society thereby bringing insight as to whether the exposure of society to the project's activities on the ground can bring about a strongly desired 'awareness pull' to the benefits to be reaped from healthy soils, thereby leveraging society at large to subscribe to the projects' motto: ISLANDR for Soil Health!

Introduction

The ISLANDR Roadmap is a decision-making tool designed to support users engaged in contaminated site management and land redevelopment. Recognising the complexity of the remediation process, the roadmap does not prescribe a rigid set of steps but instead offers structured guidance to navigate key decisions. While it cannot map every possible choice in advance, it provides a clear direction to help users make informed and effective decisions. Adaptable to different contexts, the roadmap can be tailored to deliver user-specific insights, ensuring relevance and practical value for diverse remediation projects.

This report provides a description of all the activities that are part of the single-site journey roadmap (table 1).

- *Table 1. Overview of the different activities per phase, under the single site journey*

Identification phase

Prioritisation of inventoried sites (Top-down approach)

- Land redevelopment as a trigger (Bottom-up approach)

Suspicion of contamination

Vision/Initiative phase

Preliminary site investigation

Qualitative (preliminary) risk assessment

Preliminary business case

Planning

Exploration of a strategy

Comprehensive site investigation

Quantitative (detailed) risk assessment

Remediation and Re-use strategies

Remediation planning

Redevelopment and restoration plan

Environmental impact and social assessment (ESIA)

Business case

Communication and Dissemination Strategies

Realisation

Procurement, contracting, permits and permissions

Remediation Implementation

Restoration Implementation

Redevelopment Implementation

Control

Interaction and communication with relevant stakeholders

Maintenance

Operation and maintenance activities based on the plan

Competent authorities check compliance with remediation objectives

Interaction and communication with the broader community

1. Identification

During this phase, one or more suspected areas of land contamination are found.

1.1. Prioritisation of inventoried sites (Top-down approach to identifying individual sites)

This part of the identification phase refers to the top-down approach defined in the Soil Monitoring Law: countries should first make a database of potentially contaminated sites and evaluate if these sites are actually contaminated. In practice, the work will need some prioritization. Inventorying of potentially contaminated sites (“suspect sites”) can take place at the level of local, regional or national authorities depending on the country. This is usually followed by a process of assessment of the suspected sites to understand the risks they pose and hence assign priorities for action. This is one (but not the only) trigger for action on an individual site.

National and regional databases for potentially contaminated sites may contain a very large number of records with varying levels of information. This can also be valid for potentially contaminated sites recognized by anomaly identification algorithms. Even

when all the potentially contaminated sites have been evaluated, there may be a need for prioritisation of the sites to accelerate remediation of the most vulnerable sites.

Screening and prioritisation processes are crucial to treating contaminated sites at an early stage, when little information is available on each site. For example, already in 2005, the European Environment Agency presented the Preliminary Risk Assessment Model for the identification and assessment of problem areas for Soil contamination in Europe (PRA.MS). This model adopts scoring criteria to rank sites for the identification of problem areas. Specific routines for the assessment of human health and ecological risks are proposed. The approach envisages a pre-screening stage of potentially contaminated sites (Tier 0), based on source size criteria, and a two-tier risk assessment model (Tier 1 and Tier 2) for the identification of problem areas for soil contamination. Tier 1 and Tier 2, sequentially or independently, can be run for risk-based scoring of sites passing the Tier 0 pre-selection. The two-tiered structure of the PRA.MS model allows for the definition of input data and selection of the assessment level based on the information quality available.

Building block

Data and metadata inventories and interpolation algorithms to produce maps and identify hotspots

National and regional databases were collected for local soil contamination. In many states, national and regional authorities have already systematically and actively identified all sites where soil contamination is suspected based on evidence collected through all available means. ISLANDR provides a metadata catalogue of these local soil contamination European databases.

ISLANDR collected also rare diffuse soil contamination European databases in the metadata catalogue and the review included EU-wide, national and regional monitoring and geochemical mapping databases. Especially in the context of LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey) (EUSO) and the new Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience, spatial soil quality data interpolation methods are needed to identify contamination “hot spots” in Europe that may constitute priority sites for soil remediation. But at the scale of the European Union, soil quality data are often sparse, imprecise or clustered (SIC) and classical interpolation methods are not well suited. ISLANDR has developed a new method of interpolation of spatial soil data that is specifically designed for SIC data. The algorithm is also suitable for interpolation and hot spot detection from more detailed SIC datasets from urban environments. Because the objective is the identification of anomalies, or hot spots, the algorithm avoids the smoothing effects of classical methods, such as kriging with a variogram. The algorithm is also useful for identifying pedogeochemical background values, which are important for the application of the healthy soil criteria of Annex I of the Directive.

Please find more information on databases on local and diffuse soil contamination from the ISLANDR Deliverable D1.1 Data summary - Overview of Soil Pollution in Europe [[Link](#)]

Please read more on the interpolation algorithm and hot spot recognition from the ISLANDR Deliverable D1.2 Hot spot identification [[Link](#)]

The ISLANDR D1.2 algorithm is available as a binary R package [[iisdia_1.0.zip](#)]

The algorithm and its scientific bases are described in: Belbèze, S., Rohmer, J., Guyonnet, D., Négrel, Ph., Tarvainen, T. 2025. Improving spatial interpolation for anomaly analysis in presence of sparse, clustered or imprecise data sets. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 279, 107868.

The ISLANDR Metadata Catalogue is available from [[Link](#)]

Building block

Regional risk assessment of potentially contaminated sites

Determining whether a site is contaminated requires soil and groundwater investigations, but it is neither feasible nor cost-effective to assess all land across the EU within a short timeframe. Regional risk assessment (RRA) can support in the initial prioritisation of potentially contaminated sites. Maps, historical risks activities, historical archives, local knowledge, industrial permits and license records, administrative information, surveys of surface and groundwater quality and site inspections may provide indications that a site may be potentially

contaminated (Pizzol et al., 2011). Once the list of potentially contaminated sites is available, a prioritization according to relative risk assessment procedures can be performed to select sites where a preliminary soil investigation is required first (Van-Camp et al., 2004). These risk assessment procedures are performed at larger scales (i.e. at regional scale) and should take into account that over a regional area, impacts caused by multiple sources are distributed and often multiplied on diverse receptors through different pathways. ISLANDR proposed a GIS-based framework for regional Relative Risk Assessment (RRA) that requires, as input data, an inventory of potentially contaminated sites (PCSs) as this is expected to be progressively available under the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Law (SML). The methodology follows a stepwise, risk-based logic consistent with Article 43b of the SML, enabling prioritisation before detailed investigations. The framework was successfully tested in the ISLANDR Toulouse Test Area, demonstrating its capacity to rank PCSs, supporting early-stage decision-making at regional scale.

1.2. Other triggers

In addition to a structured process of site identification on a regional basis that takes place in some jurisdictions and is now included in the Soil Monitoring Law as stepwise identification and investigation of potentially contaminated sites, there are multiple other potential triggers for suspicion of contamination at an individual site, as listed in the Table below. If contamination is suspected then further investigation and potentially remediation (risk management) will be required, as set out in the road map.

Table 2. Potential triggers of remediation for a single site. Adapted from Bardos (2026)

Trigger	Description
Regulatory demand	Sites where an environmental or human health impact triggers an intervention from the regulator, for example, as a result of an incident or complaint.
Voluntary remediation	In this case, a site owner/manager anticipates a potential regulatory demand
Change of land use or land redevelopment	Obligations set by a spatial planning system
Other economic triggers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mergers and acquisitions • Liability management • Divestments
Repair	Dealing with defects in previous remediation work
Illegal activities	Illegally deposited wastes, drug factories
Water	Threats of contamination to water resources, to surface water or drinking water sources
Emissions from permitted processes	Requirements tend to be more stringent than for historic land contamination, e.g., requirement to clean-up to “baseline”
Accidents, spills and fires	Contamination from spillages, combustion products, and chemicals used for extinguishing

Building block

Overview of algorithms for recognition of the level of contamination

The project's input data will be all available geochemical data, including a combination of background measurements, mining surveys, and monitoring of urban and contaminated sites. These datasets will be unique and more complex, due to the anomaly-background combination of sampled populations. Techniques for anomaly detection in a dataset vary according to the type of anomalous value present: anomalous values on box plot (range outliers), anomalous values on biplot or multidimensional projection (relationship outlier), or anomalous spatial values of a given extension (spatial outliers).

Especially in the context of LUCAS (Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey) (EUSO) and the new Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience, spatial soil quality data interpolation methods are needed to identify contamination “hot spots” in Europe that may constitute priority sites for soil remediation. But at the scale of the European Union, soil quality data are often sparse, imprecise or clustered (SIC) and classical interpolation methods are not well suited. ISLANDR has developed a new method of interpolation of spatial soil data that is specifically designed for sparse, imprecise or clustered (SIC) data. The algorithm is suitable for interpolation and hot spot detection from regional and detailed SIC datasets from urban and industrial environments. Because the objective is the identification of anomalies, or hot spots, the algorithm avoids the smoothing effects of classical methods, such as kriging with a variogram. The algorithm is also useful for identifying pedo-geochemical background values, which are important for the application of the healthy soil criteria of Annex I of the Directive. ISLANDR algorithms (IISDIA for Incomplete Imprecise Spatial Data Interpolator for Anomaly analysis) enable rapid creation of contamination maps with minimal assumptions and extracting anomalies using several algorithms in the same way as experts do.

More information at: ISLANDR Deliverable D1.2 Hot spot identification [Link]

The ISLANDR IISDIA algorithm is available as a binary R package from [Link]

The algorithm and its scientific bases are described in: Belbèze, S., Rohmer, J., Guyonnet, D., Négrel, Ph., Tarvainen, T. 2025. Improving spatial interpolation for anomaly analysis in presence of sparse, clustered or imprecise data sets. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 279, 107868.

1.3. Suspicion of contamination

Following the prioritisation of inventoried sites or another trigger, the activity of identifying whether a site is probably contaminated takes place. If no contamination is found, then re-use strategies can be explored. In some cases, potential soil contamination can be ruled out if there is comprehensive information on earlier land use. However, if some contamination is found, then other steps need to be taken to ensure that the problem is understood and the necessary steps are taken to prevent any harm to humans or the environment.

The decision of the need for the following activities (vision/initiative) lays on the data gathered during the previous activity

ISLANDR provides building block T6.1 on the policy context on EU level to support this activity.

Building block
Policy context

According to Soil monitoring law Member States should prepare a list of potentially contaminating activities and set non-binding sustainable target values and threshold values for heavy metal concentrations and nationally selected organic contaminant concentrations in soil. In the identification phase, one of the key questions can be: “Is the site potentially contaminated and is it clear who is liable?”. For the liability issues, the most relevant regulation is the Liability directive (2004/35/CE): liability for remediation; Note: not applicable if contamination took place before 30 April 2007. Depending on contaminating activities other directives and regulations might also be relevant (D6.1 Figure 4). ISLANDR D6.1 includes a checklist of such EU-level regulations. The way how these are nationally implemented in the Member States can vary.
More information at: [ISLANDR D6.1 Report on the policy framework [Link]]

2. Vision / Initiative

During this phase, the site owner, or another project promote (e.g. a community action group, a site developer, a tenant etc), develops a first concept of how a site could be used for a particular purpose.

2.1. Preliminary Site investigation

If contamination is suspected, a preliminary site investigation serves to set up an initial conceptual site model (CSM), identify potential source-pathway-receptor linkages and support qualitative risk estimation. A Conceptual Site Model (CSM) is a visual or written representation of a site, focusing on the relationships between contaminant sources, potential exposure pathways, and receptors, helping to understand and manage risks. Typically, a preliminary site investigation includes:

- Collecting basic site information
- Setting objectives, e.g. clarifying intended use, and collating historical information about past uses and activities
- Describing land use and setting (e.g., size, topography, microclimate; current and planned use, ecology, access, security, infrastructure, etc.
- Reviewing contextual, geological, and hydrogeological records for the site, including aquifers and surface water features
- Site inspection (walkover)
- Identifying material deposits, such as soil stockpiles, that will require management

- Identifying potential receptors (communities, site users, water, ecology etc.) and potential exposure pathways (e.g. air)

ISLANDR provides building block on relevant technical publication and legislation to consider supporting this activity.

<p>ADDITIONAL Building block Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice</p>
<p>The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.</p> <p>https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book</p>
<p>Building block Relevant legislation to consider</p>
<p>Relevant directives and regulations in the vision phase of the ISLANDR roadmap include particularly the Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law), Directives on public communication and engagement, Industrial Emissions Directive, Water Framework Directive and daughter directives, Environmental Liability Directive, Waste Directive and when relevant e.g. regulation on persistent organic pollutants (POP), Hg regulation, Public procurement Directive, Habitat and Birds Directives, Nature Restoration regulation, Invasive species regulation, REACH and CLP as well as Extractive Waste Directive. The way how these are nationally implemented in the Member States can vary.</p> <p>ISLANDR includes a checklist of EU level regulations (D6.1 Fig. 4) which are useful to identify contaminating activities, and areas causing environmental risks. As Soil Monitoring Law (Article 13) points out, the public concerned shall be given effective opportunities to provide timely information and to provide comments to the risk-based and stepwise approach. It is important to know who the key stakeholders are. Stakeholder engagement measures should start already at this phase and continue throughout the project.</p> <p>More information at: [ISLANDR D6.1 Report on the policy framework Link]</p>

2.2. Qualitative (Preliminary) Risk Assessment

Qualitative risk assessment is the first tier of assessment on a suspect site encompassing:

- Hazard identification = identifying and documenting contaminant sources
- Initial hazard characterisation based on listing potential contaminant linkages between the sources found and potential pathways and receptors
- Initial risk estimation

It links with preliminary site investigation. Where there are no potential source-pathway-receptor linkages, and there is little uncertainty about this, then the site is usually designated, from a regulatory point of view, as not contaminated. This determination is strictly related to the land use. Record keeping needed in case of change of use.

The CSM is updated by the outcomes of the preliminary risk assessment. If no unacceptable risks are found, the site is deemed uncontaminated, as noted above. If there are potentially significant risks, then detailed site investigation and quantitative risk assessment will be required later in the process.

ISLANDR provides building blocks on specific contaminants, geochemical backgrounds, on Sustainable Risk-based Land Management, methods and tools for risk assessment, risk assessment, and contaminants of emergent concern to support this activity.

ADDITIONAL Building block
Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

Building block
Information on the specific contaminants and goals of protection to consider

Relevant directives and regulations in the vision phase of ISLANDR roadmap, especially linked to preliminary risk assessment include Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive, Water Framework Directive and daughter directives, Environmental quality standards Directive, POPs regulation, Hg regulation, Waste Directive, Environmental Liability Directive, REACH and CLP, Directive on public communication and engagement and depending on type of contaminated site possibly e.g. Habitat and Birds Directives, Nature Restoration regulation, Invasive species regulation and Extractive Waste Directive.

ISLANDR includes a checklist of EU-level regulations (D6.1) which are useful to identify pollutants found in the area and the risks they might cause. Stakeholder engagement measures continue in accordance with the requirement of the Soil Monitoring Law.

More information at: [ISLANDR D6.1 Report on the policy framework Link]

Building block
Overview of geochemical backgrounds and elements associated with risks

Geochemical background concentration of potentially harmful elements derives from natural geological and pedological processes. According to the Soil Monitoring Law, natural and anthropogenic background levels shall be taken into account in the risk assessment. If natural background is the only reason leading to unacceptable risks, then the relevant soil shall be deemed to meet the healthy soil criteria provided that it is managed in such a way that an unacceptable risk to human health does not exist. Geochemical background concentrations and baselines have been studied in European-wide, national and regional soil geochemical mapping programmes, and they contain information on contaminating elements that are associated with risks to human health and the environment as well.

ISLANDR deliverable D1.1 gives overview of diffuse soil contamination databases including geochemical mappings [Link to D1.1]

ISLANDR metadata catalogue gives information on many databases related to geochemical background concentrations [Link to ISLANDR metadata catalogue]

Building block
Guidance for Sustainable Risk-based Land Management (SRBLM)

The international consensus that has emerged over the past 20-30 years is that decisions regarding contaminated sites should be made based on understanding and managing risks to human health and the wider environment, taking into account the current or planned use of the land. More recently, there has been a growing emphasis that risk management should also align with sustainable development principles. This integrated approach is known as sustainable and risk-based land management (SRBLM), and is increasingly recognized in international practice, policy, and regulation. Risk management of contaminated sites depends on knowledge of the linkages between sources, pathways and receptors, an estimation of their seriousness and the development of strategies to break linkages that lead to unacceptable risks. The sustainability of risk management can be considered at multiple stages, including: how best to manage the design and planning of any change in site use, and/or the choices made between different risk management (i.e. remediation) techniques.

ISLANDR D3.2 provides overarching guidance on the state of practice for achieving sustainable and risk based land management and highlights how this can be enhanced by consideration of (a) use of low input remediation

techniques; (b) circularity - i.e. linkage to a circular economy, (c) maximising the value of restoration to improve its economic case; (d) proper consideration of soil health.

More information at: [link]

Building block

Methods and tools for (preliminary) risk assessment

Provides methods and tools for risk assessment > To present a generic conceptual framework for risk-based assessment for specific sectorial approaches (and associated data needs and sources) to help prioritize sites according to the generic risk they pose.

More Information: (numerical tool free access here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17501164> - Tyrologou, P., Couto, N., Koukouzas, N., Makris, G., Kaija, J., Karatrantou, C., & DERYCKE, V. (2025). LandRisk: A GUI python based software to assess contaminated land risk using Source - Pathway - Receptor setting. Zenodo) - online user guide accessed here : https://youtu.be/XU8UvO_bY2E

Building block

Risk assessment, including soil health

ISLANDR project suggests using the impacts of contamination on soil health and functionality as a receptor in risk assessment and management. It has produced four major outputs: (1) a review paper analysing pesticide contamination trends across Europe and identifying regional contamination patterns and relevant pesticides and metabolites to watch; (2) a color-coded matrix evaluating soil health descriptors relevant to different land uses; (3) a matrix evaluating the impact of conventional and low-impact remediation techniques on soil functions (literature review); and (4) a gamified approach design to gather different stakeholders' perspectives on soil health descriptors. This contributes to the development of a decision tree that integrates contamination, land use-specific soil health descriptors, and the impact of LIRT techniques on soil functionality to integrate soil health into contaminated land management.

More information at: [link]

Building block

List of CEC to be considered in soils for prioritisation purposes

This prioritization method relies on a multi-criteria, risk-based prioritization framework for soil contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) at national and EU scales, structured around the Source–Pathway–Receptor (SPR) model. This prioritisation procedure relies on a structured scoring system. It begins with individual parameter scores, which are used to calculate composite scores for emission potential, environmental fate, and toxicity. These intermediate scores are then aggregated to derive a final prioritisation score, enabling a comparative assessment of contaminants based on multiple risk dimensions. The prioritisation Excel tool includes today more than 301 CECs and has produced a prioritised list of the CECs identified as the most concerning, and a complementary list of substances for which current knowledge is insufficient to allow for a reliable assessment. These results incorporates both risk scores and confidence indicators. This dual approach not only allows substances to be targeted for priority monitoring and/or to be considered for future soil regulations but also guides research efforts towards critical data gaps.

The excel tool and the CECs lists will be freely available online in the ISLANDR website (we are waiting the validation of the deliverables).

information at: [link]

2.3. Exploring preliminary business cases

During the development of the preliminary business case, roadmap users explore future land uses, how these might deliver value and how they relate to the original interest in the site; a timeline for the remediation and responsible party; and the financial and economic

viability of the remediation project. This activity also includes the exploration of possible financial models and partnerships, which will inform the exploration of strategies later on. This involves an iterative process for exploring socio-economic impacts and preliminary business cases through the identification of:

- Alternative land remediation and re-use scenarios
- Wider values – including prioritisation of benefits for different groups of stakeholders and possible value creation for investors
- Linking the project-relevant costs and benefits to specific beneficiaries or payers to identify possible investors for the project and develop the business case
- Relevant timelines for different scenarios.

ISLANDR provides building blocks on criteria for EU funding, Quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits, wider value exploration and prioritisation to support SRBLM, Support for developing a business case, and overview of barriers and solutions, to support this activity.

<p>Building block Criteria for EU funding (taxonomy rules)</p>
<p>EU's taxonomy regulation sets out four overarching conditions for environmentally sustainable funding and Commission delegated regulation sets technical screening criteria for activity contributing substantially to contamination prevention and control and screening criteria for economic activity causing significant harm to environmental objectives (See Chapter 4.7.1 in the ISLANDR D6.1) More information at: [ISLANDR D6.1 Horizontal policy integration / Report on the policy framework link]</p>
<p>Building block Support for the quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits</p>
<p>Provides practical and methodological support for the quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits (economic values) by 1) providing a searchable database containing economic valuation studies and economic values, some of which are suitable for value transfer, and 2) a compilation of economic valuation methods that have been applied in various studies in the brownfield remediation and redevelopment context. More information at: ISLANDR D4.1 [link] and ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Wider value exploration and prioritisation to support SRBLM</p>
<p>ISLANDR provides support for the envisioning, identifying and prioritising wider values for alternative land use and remediation scenarios in collaboration with relevant stakeholders using a gamified workshop approach based on a checklist of wider values, related indicators and a vision creation exercise. The purpose is to raise awareness among decision-makers and investors that values beyond strictly financial considerations may be critical when deciding how to sustainably remediate and redevelop a site, particularly where the direct financial case is marginal or even negative. More information at: ISLANDR D3.2 [link] and ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Support for developing a business case</p>
<p>Provides support for developing a business case accounting for wider values and evaluating the potential costs and benefits relating to the site remediation and reuse strategies. The purpose is to provide a framework which supports a local project economic analysis to evaluate the 1) potential financial return on investment, 2) potential social return on investment, and 3) opportunities for internalization of wider values as alternative sources of revenue or reduced costs to improve the value proposition for such projects and identification of different financial mechanisms to develop a blended finance strategy. More information at: ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Overview of barriers and solutions</p>
<p>Countries vary in terms of legal, institutional and financial/economic frameworks when it comes to the remediation and regeneration of contaminated land. Depending on their context and legal, institutional and financial/economic development, all countries in some way experience barriers on their road to land remediation. ISLANDR provides an inventory of barriers countries might experience, depending on their legal, institutional and</p>

financial/economic contexts and phase of their remediation journey and proposes possible solutions to overcome those identified barriers. The barrier inventory was conducted through a literature search and complemented with a survey of the ISLANDR participating countries through workshops and conferences.

While the inventory was carried out in country level, this building block is mostly useful for policy-makers and certain authorities.

More information at: [Barriers and solutions for the reuse of contaminated land and soils in the ISLANDR Deliverable D5.1 Report Link]

Building block
Guidance for Sustainable Risk-based Land Management (SRBLM)

ISLANDR Deliverable 3.2 describes how the underlying sustainable and risk-based land management philosophy can be applied while exploring preliminary business cases. ISLANDR D3.2 provides overarching guidance on the state of practice for achieving sustainable and risk based land management and highlights how this can be enhanced by consideration of (a) use of low input remediation techniques; (b) circularity – i.e. linkage to a circular economy, (c) maximising the value of restoration to improve its economic case; (d) proper consideration of soil health.

More information at: [Link to D3.2]

2.4. Communication and dissemination strategies

In this face, there is a need to recognize the relevant stakeholder. The interaction and communication with relevant stakeholders and the broader community during this phase focuses on bringing them on board.

Building block
Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR Roadmap

In the Deliverable D6.2, ISLANDR has examined how the ISLANDR roadmap can serve SRBLM of contaminated sites in different European settings

The document draws from qualitative data gathered via focus groups, interviews and a workshop in the ISLANDR test areas (ITAs). Learning from institutional arrangements and practices allows us to identify supportive roles the roadmap can gain in different settings. Although the ITAs necessarily act as mere examples of the diversity of European conditions, the data generated through engagement with regional and national practitioners such as authorities, site owners, consultants and NGO representatives, provide understanding of the types of practical challenges the actors face in their everyday work. These challenges may lower the likelihood of roadmap take-up, but it is also possible that the roadmap, if adopted, could help to tackle key management challenges.

Link [D6.2 Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR roadmap. Policy paper - Proposal of measures to promote institutional adaptability]

ADDITIONAL Building block
Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

3.Planning

This wrap-around phase can include multiple activities and is the process by which the vision is elaborated to finally arrive at detailed action plans.

3.1. Detailed Site Investigation

Where a site has been identified as potentially contaminated on the basis of qualitative risk assessment, a more intrusive site investigation is carried out to provide information to support quantitative risk assessment. Activities include:

Field sampling, e.g.

- Trial pits
- Direct-push sampling,
- Sampling based on drilling methods,
- Passive diffusion bag samplers,
- Soil gas sampling,
- Single and continuous water sampling,
- Integral pumping tests

Also use field analytical methods

Sample preparation and dispatch for off-site laboratory analytical methods, treatability studies, etc.

The CSM is updated accordingly to include additional site information and the outcomes of the detailed (quantitative) risk assessment.

ADDITIONAL Building block

Technical publication on sustainable and risk based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

3.2. Quantitative (Detailed) Risk Assessment

The site-specific risk assessment is a tiered process, and it takes place if the preliminary risk assessment indicates potentially significant risks. This typically begins by comparing contaminant concentrations found in samples (such as soil and groundwater) taken from the site or its surroundings with threshold concentrations that the regulator (or other widely accepted body) has established (i.e. screening or generic risk assessment). This is done by comparing soil and water analytical findings with generic thresholds, which may be linked to the anticipated end use of the site. Generic thresholds are generally very conservative and hence, if they are not exceeded, there is no need to go to site-specific risk assessment. However, for risks to groundwater, additional information and thresholds related to the leachability of contamination may also be needed. In some cases, where there is doubt over the relevance of these generic thresholds then a “site-specific quantitative risk assessment” is carried out. This may involve the derivation of site-specific thresholds, based on methodologies accepted by the regulator, or occasionally a complete modelling of likely daily intakes of contaminants, which is compared against acceptable doses, i.e. safe exposure levels.

ISLANDR provides building block on high priority CECs to support this activity.

Building block**Risk-based prioritisation framework and identification of high priority CECs**

The prioritization method relies on a multi-criteria, risk-based prioritization framework for soil contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) at national and EU scales, structured around the Source–Pathway–Receptor (SPR) model. This prioritisation procedure is based on a structured scoring system. It begins with individual parameter scores, which are used to calculate composite scores for emission potential, environmental fate, and toxicity. These intermediate scores are then aggregated to derive a final prioritisation score, enabling a comparative assessment of contaminants based on multiple risk dimensions. The prioritisation Excel tool includes today more than 301 CECs and has produced a prioritised list of the CECs identified as the most concerning, and a complementary list of substances for which current knowledge is insufficient to allow for a reliable assessment. These results incorporates both risk scores and confidence indicators. This prioritization method identifies CECs soils most at risk of causing large-scale contamination.

The excel tool and the CECs lists will be freely available online in the ISLANDR website (we are waiting the validation of the deliverables).

information at: [\[link\]](#)

ADDITIONAL Building block**Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice**

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/srblm-book>

3.3. Exploration of a remediation strategy

Using information from previous activities, the strategy exploration assesses alternative approaches to determine their feasibility and suitability for the site. This includes reviewing site history, particularly any potentially contaminative uses, relevant regulatory requirements and preliminary risk information, noting that under the Soil Monitoring Law a site-specific risk assessment may not be required if existing information is sufficient to justify soil remediation. Remediation options are screened to address unacceptable risks, defining priorities, timelines and remediation targets, and identifying appropriate technical solutions such as containment, in situ treatment or soil excavation. The strategy also considers opportunities for wider value creation, including social benefits and complementary services such as renewable energy, carbon management or sustainable drainage, alongside constraints related to space, time and budget. A shared vision for site restoration and reuse is developed with stakeholders, supported by early engagement with investors and funders, and informed by an initial site layout that balances remediation needs with sustainable re-use, potential services and interim uses. Potential socio-economic impacts are also considered, recognising that these activities may occur in parallel through collaboration between planners and remediators.

Building block**Guidance for Sustainable Risk-based Land Management (SRBLM)**

The international consensus that has emerged over the past 20-30 years is that decisions regarding contaminated sites should be made based on understanding and managing risks to human health and the wider environment, considering the current or planned use of the land. More recently, there has been a growing

emphasis that risk management should also align with sustainable development principles. This integrated approach is known as sustainable and risk-based land management (SRBLM), and is increasingly recognized in international practice, policy, and regulation. Risk management of contaminated sites depends on knowledge of the linkages between sources, pathways and receptors, an estimation of their seriousness and the development of strategies to break linkages that lead to unacceptable risks. The sustainability of risk management can be considered at multiple stages, including the choices made between different risk management (i.e. remediation) techniques.

ISLANDR D3.2 provides overarching guidance on the state of practice for achieving sustainable and risk based land management and highlights how this can be enhanced by consideration of (a) use of low input remediation techniques; (b) circularity - i.e. linkage to a circular economy, (c) maximising the value of restoration to improve its economic case; (d) proper consideration of soil health.

Building block

Remediation appraisal tool / EICLAR

ISLANDR has been supporting the extension of an online decision support tool (from the Enhanced Innovative In situ Biotechnologies for Contaminated Land Remediation (EiCLaR) project) for option appraisal: Selection and benchmarking of remediation, which can be localised to different site areas or S-P-R linkages.

Web platform contaminatedland.info is a dedicated resource for the sustainable management and remediation of contaminated sites. This platform has a focus on sustainable and risk-based land management, and it offers information on best practices, regulatory considerations, and innovative solutions for addressing contamination challenges.

The site features a remediation option screening tool, allowing you to compare 24 categories of remediation technologies to assist you in selecting the most effective approach for your site. The user can also access training podcasts, case studies, and a regularly updated news feed covering the latest developments in remediation and environmental policy.

An enquiry panel is available to provide expert guidance on site-specific issues. For those seeking a deeper understanding of sustainable remediation strategies, contaminatedland.info offers direct access to a major publication on sustainable and risk-based land management, ensuring you have access to the latest research and industry knowledge.

More information at: <https://contaminatedland.info/>

Building block

Circularity assessment guidance

Circular economy assessment tool that can be used to compare remediation strategies *ex-ante* (planning stage) to see how far they contribute to circular economy.

Remediation activities are inherently linked to the circular economy, as one of their primary targets is to bring new usefulness to natural resources that would otherwise be disposed or remain unused. On the other hand, some technological solutions may conflict with the implementation of circular economy principles. Excavation with landfill disposal completely removes soil identified as waste and often shifts the problem to landfills; high-intensity thermal treatments alter soil structure and functionality, preventing its recovery “in situ”. Adopting more sustainable and circular practices can offer new opportunities to minimise waste production and promote the regeneration and reuse of materials and resources. It is therefore necessary to complement sustainability assessment with a circularity assessment, which has recently been standardised by ISO 59020:2024 “Circular economy – Measuring and assessing circularity performance” and UNI/TS 11820:2024 “Measuring circularity – Methods and indicators for measuring circular processes in organizations”. To this end, a set of circularity indicators suitable for the circularity assessment of remediation technologies has been identified. This assessment, carried out during the design (*ex-ante*) phase of the intervention, is useful for distinguishing between different technological solutions based on their adherence to the principles of the circular economy.

More information at: [link]

ADDITIONAL Building block

Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

3.4. Remediation and Re-use Strategies

Remediation (or risk reduction actions) describes interventions on contaminated sites carried out to prevent, minimize or mitigate harm to receptors such as human health, property, or the wider environment. This mitigation is achieved by breaking any of the S-P-R linkage. Remediation actions take place at the level of the source or the pathway, although they may be combined with receptor-level controls, such as risk reduction based on restrictions on allowable land use. The elaboration of remediation strategies uses the CSM as its basis to identify the risk management requirements the remediation should provide for, and the nature of the site, which affects the suitability and feasibility of different remediation processes.

Hence the re-use of a site has a critical determining impact on risk management (and so remediation) needs. The configuration of a site should be optimised to combine the uses of particular areas with minimising remediation efforts by, for example, matching land use needs such as car parking with areas where the sustainability impact of achieving a more multifunctional purpose would be excessively high. The spatial planning context of the specific uses across a site is therefore very important, especially in larger areas.

ISLANDR provides building blocks on excavated soil reuse, soil-inclusive planning and design, the monetary valuation of benefits, and wider values and linkages to sustainability to support this activity.

ADDITIONAL Building block

Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

Building block

Guidance document for excavated soil reuse

A paper that will be submitted to a journal in 2026 which sets out a survey of regional management systems that encourage a circular economy for excavated soil management and a series of suggestions for a model excavated soil management system in regions without one. More relevant for policy and regulatory experts than site owners in DL6.3.

More information at: [link] and [link]

<p>Building block Guidance on soil inclusive planning and design</p> <p>Provides guidance on soil-inclusive planning and design by inventorying and analysing soil remediation and spatial planning models and instruments, examining how soil health is integrated.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about existing strategies to guide soil-inclusive site planning and design - Information about existing instruments that can influence the way soil remediation and redevelopment is conducted <p>More information at: [Guidance on Soil-inclusive Planning and Design from ISLANDR Deliverable D5.2 Link]</p>
<p>Building block Criteria to prioritise strategies</p> <p>Qualitative method to rank different remediation and re-use strategies in terms of their environmental, social, economic, human and technical aspects.</p> <p>More information on the Ranking for the Strategies from ISLANDR can be found in Deliverable D5.2 Report [Link]</p> <p>Excel-based tool to conduct a quick analysis to rank potential strategies based on environmental, human, social, economic and technical aspects. Stakeholders involved in remediation and redevelopment can utilise the tool to quickly screen the performance of different strategies against the set criteria and adjust the weights according to their priorities.</p> <p>More information at: [link]</p>
<p>Building block Wider value exploration and prioritisation to support SRBLM</p> <p>ISLANDR provides support for the envisioning, identifying and prioritising wider values for alternative land use and remediation scenarios in collaboration with relevant stakeholders using a gamified workshop approach based on a checklist of wider values, related indicators and a vision creation exercise. The purpose is to raise awareness among decision-makers and investors that values beyond strictly financial considerations may be critical when deciding how to sustainably remediate and redevelop a site, particularly where the direct financial case is marginal or even negative.</p> <p>More information at: ISLANDR D3.2 [link] and ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Support for developing a business case</p> <p>Provides support for developing a business case accounting for wider values and evaluating the potential costs and benefits relating to the site remediation and reuse strategies. The purpose is to provide a framework which supports a local project economic analysis to evaluate the 1) potential financial return on investment, 2) potential social return on investment, and 3) opportunities for internalization of wider values as alternative sources of revenue or reduced costs to improve the value proposition for such projects and identification of different financial mechanisms to develop a blended finance strategy.</p> <p>More information at: ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Remediation appraisal tool / EICLAR</p> <p>ISLANDR has been supporting the extension of an online decision support tool for option appraisal: Selection and benchmarking of remediation, which can be localised to different site areas or S-P-R linkages.</p> <p>Web platform contaminatedland.info is a dedicated resource for the sustainable management and remediation of contaminated sites. This platform has a focus on sustainable and risk-based land management, and it offers information on best practices, regulatory considerations, and innovative solutions for addressing contamination challenges.</p> <p>The site features a remediation option screening tool, allowing you to compare 24 categories of remediation technologies to assist you in selecting the most effective approach for your site. The user can also access training podcasts, case studies, and a regularly updated news feed covering the latest developments in remediation and environmental policy.</p> <p>An enquiry panel is available to provide expert guidance on site-specific issues. For those seeking a deeper understanding of sustainable remediation strategies, contaminatedland.info offers direct access to a major publication on sustainable and risk-based land management, ensuring you have access to the latest research and industry knowledge.</p>

More information at: <https://contaminatedland.info/>

Building block LIRT Verification paper

Particularly at TRL8 or 9 there may be good reasons to verify LIRT claims for low resource and energy intensity, use of renewables and delivery of wider benefits. This verification can then support future deployments of the LIRT, and document evidence that low resource and energy intensity, use of renewables and delivery of wider benefits have been achieved. ISLANDR provides a position paper on LIRT verification which is relevant at the PLANNING stage (verification planning), REALISATION stage (data collection) and MAINTENANCE Stage (reporting and ongoing monitoring, especially for long term land management solutions).

Building block link: Annex 2 of DL 3.2

3.5. Remediation planning

Remediation planning consists of two phases: option appraisal and remediation planning itself. Option appraisal is the process of evaluating how well different remediation approaches can meet the objectives agreed for a site. There are three domains within this comparison: the achievement of the necessary risk management, cost-effectiveness and sustainability. Option appraisal is an iterative process with a long list of possible approaches identified, which is then gradually shortened based on what approaches best fit a site and its needs. Option appraisal is carried out based on the CSM. The wider context of contaminated site projects makes sustainability assessment a crucial component of option appraisal. The remediation work may not deliver the complete risk management process, which may also rely on a series of interventions at the receptor level in particular institutional controls. Institutional controls describe controls put in place by authorities, for example planning restrictions (e.g. must be zoned for industry), prohibitions / permits (e.g. temporary suspension of drinking water well etc; controls on movement of excavated materials etc) and very commonly end-use limits related to risk assessment (e.g. risk based remediation thresholds support use for houses with gardens, living space without gardens, public open space, industry etc – varies country by country)

Following the option appraisal, the remediation planning encompasses the detailed planning of the remediation work to be undertaken as a remediation plan, to deliver the remediation operationally and ensure that objectives have been met.

ISLANDR provides building blocks on excavated soil reuse and the regulatory framework to support this activity.

ADDITIONAL Building block Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice

The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.

<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/srblm-book>

Building block Guidance for excavated soil reuse

A paper that will be submitted to a journal in 2026 which sets out a survey of regional management systems that encourage a circular economy for excavated soil management and a series of suggestions for a model excavated

soil management system in regions without one. More relevant for policy and regulatory experts than site owners in D6.3.

More information at: [\[link\]](#) and [\[link\]](#)

Building block

Information on the principles and regulatory thresholds to consider

According to the Soil Monitoring Law, in case the site has been found to be contaminated, one should either carry out a site-specific risk assessment to identify the appropriate risk reduction measures or take remediation actions. The latter option should be selected when site-specific risk assessment brings only little added value for decision-making or if the cost-benefit analysis favours remediation actions instead. Thresholds may be considered based on national thresholds established defined by Member States in accordance with the Soil Monitoring Law. If soil contamination causes a risk of contamination or has already resulted in the contamination of other environment compartments, then relevant environmental quality directive standards, water and air quality standards should be considered, depending on the medium. ISLANDR provides a description of the legislation that should be considered in the remediation planning (D6.1). This includes both legislation to be followed in all or most cases, e.g. waste regulations, and specific legislation that needs to be considered only in some specific cases, e.g. POPs regulations, regulation on invasive alien species.

More information at: D6.1 Horizontal policy integration -report [\[link\]](#)

3.6. Redevelopment and restoration plan

Once the remediation plan has taken place, the redevelopment and restoration plans can be elaborated, building on the initial ambitions outlined in the exploration of the strategy.

Redevelopment plans involve a change in the land use, while restoration plans consider returning the land to its original state before contamination focusing on the improvement of natural ecosystems. However, land use is not the only consideration, and a comprehensive perspective needs to be taken to ensure that all necessary regulations, limitations and ambitions are incorporated in the plans. For example, national or regional spatial planning instruments might set a development vision that sets a general direction for the redevelopment, with municipal plans and regulations defining the boundary conditions for a site-level intervention (e.g. building occupancy percentage of a site, minimum green area, etc.). Likewise, the restoration of a site will likely be more connected to environmental regulations and specific government ambitions and targets. Usually, a redevelopment plan includes:

- Vision and goals, aligned with the relevant regulations
- Engagement of the community, promoting their buy-in into the project
- Assessment of the context from a spatial planning perspective
- Master planning
- Technical feasibility
- Timeline and phasing plan
- Monitoring and maintenance of the goals and targets initially established

Restoration, on the other hand, focuses on the improvement of the natural ecosystems and implies going back to a natural condition of the land in terms of soil fertility, carbon storage, biodiversity, and water regulation. The specific activities will likely include, among others, nature-based practices and robust monitoring and maintenance to assess the success of the restoration.

ISLANDR provides building block on soil-inclusive planning and design to support this activity.

Building block
Guidance on soil-inclusive planning and design

Provides guidance on soil-inclusive planning and design by inventorying and analysing soil remediation and spatial planning models and instruments, examining how soil health is integrated.

- Provides information about existing strategies to guide soil-inclusive planning and design in ITAs
- Provides information about existing instruments that can influence the way soil remediation and redevelopment is conducted

More information at: [Guidance on Soil-inclusive Planning and Design from ISLANDR Deliverable D5.2 Link]

3.7. Environmental and social impact assessment (ESIA)

An Environmental and social impact assessment (ESIA) is a process to determine the potential risks that a project might pose to soil quality and the environment, and it is usually developed together with environmental and social management plans (ESMPs). Local regulations as well as several funders usually request this type of assessment before projects are implemented. For example, the World Bank describes these types of assessments as “key tools for identifying and assessing social and environmental risks and benefits at the planning stage of an investment, and for building risk mitigation measures into project design and implementation.” (UNCTAD & World Bank, 2018).

An ESMP should consider aspects such as (UNCTAD & World Bank, 2018) the management of environmental and social risks and impacts, contamination prevention and management, community health and safety, land rights, land acquisition and involuntary resettlement, and stakeholder engagement and information disclosure, among others.

ADDITIONAL Building block
Example: Environmental and Social Assessment (ESIA) report by World Bank

The World Bank describes these types of assessments as “key tools for identifying and assessing social and environmental risks and benefits at the planning stage of an investment, and for building risk mitigation measures into project design and implementation.” (UNCTAD & World Bank, 2018).

Link: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/505181550816224108/pdf/Final-ESIA-Report-10-May-2018.pdf>

3.8. Business case

Iterative process for selection of remediation and re-use strategies and development of a viable business case includes:

- Selection of land remediation and re-use strategy
- Valuation of prioritised economic wider values
- Financial and economic analysis to develop expanded value proposition for identified remediation and re-use strategy

- Involving potential investors (public, private and societal) and exploring financial mechanisms to develop a blended finance strategy
- Informing and communicating with relevant stakeholders

ISLANDR provides building block on Quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits, and Support for developing a business case, to support this activity.

<p>Building block Support for the quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits</p>
<p>Provides practical and methodological support for the quantification and monetary valuation of wider benefits (economic values) by 1) providing a searchable database containing economic valuation studies and economic values, some of which are suitable for value transfer, and 2) a compilation of economic valuation methods that have been applied in various studies in the brownfield remediation and redevelopment context. More information at: ISLANDR D4.1 [link] and ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>
<p>Building block Support for developing a business case</p>
<p>Provides support for developing a business case accounting for wider values and evaluating the potential costs and benefits relating to the site remediation and reuse strategies. The purpose is to provide a framework which supports a local project economic analysis to evaluate the 1) potential financial return on investment, 2) potential social return on investment, and 3) opportunities for internalization of wider values as alternative sources of revenue or reduced costs to improve the value proposition for such projects and identification of different financial mechanisms to develop a blended finance strategy. More information at: ISLANDR D4.2 [link]</p>

3.9. Communication and Dissemination Strategies

Effective communication and dissemination strategies are implemented mainly across the planning phase. These strategies vary depending on the country and context. In some countries, co-creation with stakeholders including permitting authorities plays a central role in ensuring that all relevant parties are involved in the planning and decision-making process, fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration. Additionally, a key aspect of these strategies is branding the site and defining its identity. This involves creating a clear and distinctive image for the site, which helps in building recognition, trust, and engagement with the intended audience. The process of branding ensures that the remediation project communicates its purpose and values clearly, establishing a strong connection with users and stakeholders alike.

<p>Building block Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR Roadmap</p>
<p>In the Deliverable D6.2, ISLANDR has examined how the ISLANDR roadmap can serve SRBLM of contaminated sites in different European settings The document draws from qualitative data gathered via focus groups, interviews and a workshop in the ISLANDR test areas (ITAs). Learning from institutional arrangements and practices allows us to identify supportive roles the roadmap can gain in different settings. Although the ITAs necessarily act as mere examples of the diversity of European conditions, the data generated through engagement with regional and national practitioners such as authorities, site owners, consultants and NGO representatives, provide understanding of the types of practical challenges the actors face in their everyday work. These challenges may lower the likelihood of roadmap take-up, but it is also possible that the roadmap, if adopted, could help to tackle key management challenges. Link [D6.2 Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR roadmap. Policy paper - Proposal of measures to promote institutional adaptability]</p>

<p>ADDITIONAL Building block Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice</p>
<p>The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.</p> <p>https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/srblm-book</p>

4. Realisation

During the realisation phase, contracts are let and practical delivery activities take place on site.

REALISATION

4.1. Procurement, contracting, permits and permissions

Procurement of the required services is the first step in the realisation of remediation activities, followed by contracting. Depending on the type and scale of contamination and how the remediation is implemented, a permit or several permits may be required before the activities can be started. It is also possible that only a permission/notification is needed. The required procedure and the responsible authorities vary across the member states and are defined in each MS's national legislation.

Building block EU principles of public procurement (PP)
<p>ISLANDR D6.1 provides a description of the Directive on public procurement that public bodies need to follow in their purchases. The directive includes generic rules and sets monetary thresholds when tendering procedure (Chapter 4.9.3). While the monetary thresholds have been set at the EU level, Member States can follow their own, lower national thresholds. Organizations, too, can set their own thresholds that are lower than the national and/or EU-wide ones.</p> <p>More information at: D6.1 Horizontal policy integration -report [link]</p>
Building block Support for procurement practices to promote sustainable remediation
<p>ISLANDR D6.3 describes the role of procurement in attaining SRBLM and gives examples of good practices as well as recommendations to support it.</p> <p>Link to D6.3 [link]</p>
ADDITIONAL Building block Innovation procurement and socially responsible public procurement (SRPP)
<p>The European Commission provides guidance for innovation procurement that will, per its definition support Europe's green transition and sustainable growth, among others.</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/45975/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/native</p> <p>In addition, the Commission provides guidance and examples of good practices of SRPP.</p> <p>https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/public-procurement/strategic-procurement/socially-responsible-public-procurement_en</p>

4.2. Remediation implementation

The remediation phase includes all activities that aim to ensure that the appropriate risk reduction measures are taken and implemented to reduce to an acceptable risk to human health and the environment. Common remediation activities are:

- **Capping:** Placing a protective layer over contaminated areas, such as soil or sediment, to prevent exposure.
- **Excavation:** Removing contaminated soil or sediment and replacing it with clean material.
- **Chemical In Situ Treatment:** Applying chemicals to neutralize or immobilize contaminants, such as using activated carbon to absorb toxins.
- **Pump-and-Treat Systems:** Extracting contaminated groundwater, treating it at the surface, and then re-injecting or safely discharging it.
- **Thermal In Situ Treatment:** Using heat to vaporize or destroy pollutants, often applied to contaminated soil or sludge.

- **Air Sparging:** Injecting air into groundwater to volatilize and remove volatile organic compounds (VOCs).
- **Bioremediation (in situ or ex situ):** Using microorganisms, fungi, or plants to break down or absorb harmful substances.
- **Phytoremediation:** Planting vegetation that naturally absorbs or stabilizes contaminants from soil or water.

The type of contamination or remediation determines the remediation activities. In the remediation plan, the remediation activities and the level of necessary remediation that should be reached are indicated. The remediation activities are tailored to the specific type and extent of contamination, to the socio-economic and regulatory context and the decisions made in the prior phases. In most EU regions, regulatory agencies oversee remediation projects to ensure they meet legal and environmental standards.

ISLANDR provides building block on the excavated soil passport to support this activity.

<p>Building block Guidance for excavated soil reuse</p>
<p>A paper that will be submitted to a journal in 2026 which sets out a survey of regional management systems that encourage a circular economy for excavated soil management and a series of suggestions for a model excavated soil management system in regions without one. More relevant for policy and regulatory experts than site owners in D6.3. More information at: [link] and [link]</p>
<p>Building block LIRT Verification paper</p>
<p>Particularly at TRL8 or 9 there may be good reasons to verify LIRT claims for low resource and energy intensity, use of renewables and delivery of wider benefits. This verification can then support future deployments of the LIRT, and document evidence that low resource and energy intensity, use of renewables and delivery of wider benefits have been achieved. ISLANDR provides a position paper on LIRT verification which is relevant at the PLANNING stage (verification planning), REALISATION stage (data collection) and MAINTENANCE Stage (reporting and ongoing monitoring, especially for long term land management solutions).</p> <p>Building block link: Annex 2 of D3.2</p>
<p>Building block Information on the regulatory benchmarks</p>
<p>There is no single set of EU-wide benchmarks for soil because the specific contaminants and the required cleanup levels vary significantly depending on the site and its intended use. Conditions imposed in the environmental permit for the remediation project should ensure the implementation of environmental protection in accordance with existing regulations, Baseline for soil quality determined according to requirements of IED is used as a benchmark to define the soil remediation need when the activity is ceased. Benchmarks for the quality of surface water and groundwater are set in the directive on environmental quality standards and groundwater directive. During the remediation implementation it is important to follow EU directives on health and safety at work which include exposure limit values that are indicative values for assessment of occupational risks, as well as the quality criteria for ambient air. This building block provides a report that includes the information on the relevant EU-level regulatory benchmarks to consider when implementing remediation actions.</p> <p>More information at: D6.1 Horizontal policy integration -report [link]</p>

4.3. Restoration Implementation

[No change in land use] Restoration of the area includes all activities that help to bring back a prior state. Anthropogenic use, natural hazards or contamination can change the state of the area. The difference between restoration and redevelopment is that following

redevelopment, there is a different use of the area than before. With restoration of the area, the same land use (nature, agriculture etc.) is pursued as before.

4.4. Redevelopment Implementation

[Change in land use] Redevelopment activities are specific actions undertaken to transform and repurpose a site. Common redevelopment activities are:

- Demolition and Clearing: Removing existing structures or debris to prepare the site for new development.
- Infrastructure Development: Building or upgrading utilities, roads, and other necessary (subsurface) infrastructure to support the new use of the site.
- Construction: Constructing new buildings, facilities, or public spaces.
- Landscaping and Beautification: Enhancing the site's appearance through landscaping, green spaces, and aesthetic improvements.

In the redevelopment plan, the specific redevelopment activities are indicated. These activities are tailored to the specific natural as well as socio-economic and regulatory contexts and the decisions made in the prior phases.

4.5. Control

This activity involves overseeing the contractor during the implementation of the remediation, redevelopment and/or restoration plans. It includes monitoring the progress against financial aspects and overseeing compliance with the relevant legislation.

4.6. Interaction and communication with relevant stakeholders

The interaction and communication with relevant stakeholders and the broader community during this phase focuses on bringing them on board and providing grievance mechanisms to handle complaints.

Building block Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR Roadmap
<p>In the Deliverable D6.2, ISLANDR has examined how the ISLANDR roadmap can serve SRBLM of contaminated sites in different European settings</p> <p>The document draws from qualitative data gathered via focus groups, interviews and a workshop in the ISLANDR test areas (ITAs). Learning from institutional arrangements and practices allows us to identify supportive roles the roadmap can gain in different settings. Although the ITAs necessarily act as mere examples of the diversity of European conditions, the data generated through engagement with regional and national practitioners such as authorities, site owners, consultants and NGO representatives, provide understanding of the types of practical challenges the actors face in their everyday work. These challenges may lower the likelihood of roadmap take-up, but it is also possible that the roadmap, if adopted, could help to tackle key management challenges.</p> <p>Link [D6.2 Harnessing the benefits of the ISLANDR roadmap. Policy paper - Proposal of measures to promote institutional adaptability]</p>
ADDITIONAL Building block Technical publication on sustainable and risk-based land management in practice
<p>The book will provide a single coherent narrative that explains sustainable and risk-based land management from the concepts of land contamination and what triggers action on contaminated sites through to the processes of site investigation, risk assessment, risk management, and the achievement of sustainable approaches to risk management. It also includes a detailed treatment of remediation technologies and how they are implemented, taking particular account of achieving the goals of a circular economy, both in terms of</p>

the use of land and the use of soil. It provides an authoritative grounding across all of these topics with extensive citations to sources of more detailed information.
<https://contaminatedland.info/srblm-learning/sbrlm-book>

5. Maintenance

The scope of maintenance depends very much on the site context and is required during long-lasting remediation.

MAINTENANCE

5.1. Operation, maintenance and monitoring activities based on the plan

Operation and maintenance activities are crucial for ensuring the long-term success of remediation and redevelopment efforts. Operation and maintenance activities include environmental monitoring to check whether the remediation activities were sufficient to maintain the level of remediation and the reduction of risks that are associated to the contamination. Data is gathered from the site to identify and track changes in air, water, and

soil quality, to ensure that the site remains safe for its use. With adaptive monitoring the monitoring activities are flexible and responsive to changing conditions or new information. This approach allows for flexible adjustments to monitoring protocols based on evolving conditions, ensuring ongoing protection and the ability to address new challenges as they arise. Adaptive monitoring is especially important when applied to new concepts such as soil health, because new knowledge regarding soil health is currently being developed. Additionally, maintenance activities can include the treatment of contaminated groundwater and maintenance/removal of vegetation in the area.

ISLANDR provides building block on long-term site reuse and aftercare in the context of SRBLM.

Building block Guidance for Sustainable Risk-based Land Management (SRBLM)
<p>The international consensus that has emerged over the past 20-30 years is that decisions regarding contaminated sites should be made based on understanding and managing risks to human health and the wider environment, considering the current or planned use of the land. More recently, there has been a growing emphasis that risk management should also align with sustainable development principles. This integrated approach is known as sustainable and risk-based land management (SRBLM), and is increasingly recognized in international practice, policy, and regulation. Risk management of contaminated sites depends on knowledge of the linkages between sources, pathways and receptors, an estimation of their seriousness and the development of strategies to break linkages that lead to unacceptable risks. The sustainability of risk management can be considered at multiple stages, including the choices made between different risk management (i.e. remediation) techniques. ISLANDR D3.2 provides overarching guidance on the state of practice for achieving sustainable and risk based land management and highlights how this can be enhanced by consideration of (a) use of low input remediation techniques; (b) circularity - i.e. linkage to a circular economy, (c) maximising the value of restoration to improve its economic case; (d) proper consideration of soil health.</p>
Building block LIRT Verification paper
<p>Particularly at TRL8 or 9 there may be good reasons to verify LIRT claims for low resource and energy intensity, use of renewables and delivery of wider benefits. This verification can then support future deployments of the LIRT, and document evidence that low resource and energy intensity, use of renewables and delivery of wider benefits have been achieved. ISLANDR provides a position paper on LIRT verification which is relevant at the PLANNING stage (verification planning), REALISATION stage (data collection) and MAINTENANCE Stage (reporting and ongoing monitoring, especially for long term land management solutions).</p> <p>Building block link: Annex 2 of D3.2</p>

5.2. Competent authorities check compliance with remediation objectives

In the remediation plan, the level of necessary remediation is indicated. In some countries, this activity consists of checking the compliance of the remediation with the set objectives and existing regulations. This is done by the competent authorities involved in remediation and compliance, which vary depending on the country.

5.3. Interaction and communication with the broader community

In this phase, this activity focuses on the communication of results to the broader community after the project has been implemented and while it is being monitored. Feedback from the community, together with the monitoring results, can be used to adapt maintenance activities if needed.

Hence the re-use of a site has a critical determining impact on risk management (and so remediation) needs. The configuration of a site should be optimised to combine the uses of particular areas with minimising remediation efforts by, for example, matching land use needs such as car parking